

Predicting CPU Burst Times with ML to Enhance Shortest Job First (SJF) and Shortest Remaining Time First (SRTF) CPU Scheduling

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Abstract—Optimizing CPU scheduling is crucial for enhancing the overall performance of operating systems, particularly in environments that run multiple processes, where responsiveness and efficient resource utilization are essential. Scheduling algorithms such as Shortest Job First (SJF) and Shortest Remaining Time First (SRTF) are theoretically effective in reducing the average waiting and turnaround times. However, their implementation in real-world systems is limited due to the need for precise knowledge of each process’s CPU burst time, which is typically unavailable during execution. Traditional methods, such as exponential averaging, often fail to provide accurate or adaptive predictions for dynamic workloads. This study explores how Machine Learning (ML) can be applied to accurately predict CPU burst times, enabling practical use of SJF and SRTF in real-time systems. This study leverages ML to predict CPU burst times, using a synthetic dataset mimicking the Grid Workload Archive (GWA-T-4) to train models including K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), Support Vector Machines (SVM), Decision Trees, Random Forest, XGBoost, and Artificial Neural Networks (ANN). The ANN and ANN+SVM ensemble achieved superior accuracy (MAE 4.12–4.13 ms, CC 0.885), significantly outperforming the baseline (MAE = 20.67 ms). These predictions enable the scheduler to make more informed decisions, leading to reduced context switching, improved resource allocation, and shorter wait and turnaround times. Moreover, this approach helps alleviate issues such as process starvation. By embedding ML into CPU scheduling, the research offers a practical solution to transform the theoretical benefits of SJF and SRTF into practical, real-world applications, contributing to the development of intelligent and adaptive operating systems.

I. INTRODUCTION

Central Processing Unit(CPU) scheduling is a fundamental aspect of operating systems, coordinating the allocation of CPU resources to various processes to optimize system performance [1]. The primary objective of a CPU scheduler is to maximize CPU utilization, increase system throughput, and minimize various metrics such as waiting time, turnaround time, and response time. Traditional algorithms such as Shortest Job First (SJF) and Shortest Remaining Time First (SRTF) have been widely recognized for their theoretical optimality in minimizing average waiting times. Other traditional CPU scheduling algorithms include First-Come, First-Served (FCFS), Priority Scheduling, Round Robin (RR), and Multilevel Queue Scheduling (MQS).

SJF is a non-preemptive scheduling algorithm where once a process starts executing, it runs to completion without interruption, even if a new process with a shorter burst time arrives. On the other hand, SRTF allows preemption, which indicates that if a new process arrives with a burst time *shorter than the remaining time* of the currently executing process, the CPU will preempt the current process and switch to the newly arrived, shorter process. Therefore, SJF and SRTF are designed to minimize the average waiting time of processes in a system, prioritizing shorter jobs, and in effect, overall system efficiency can be improved.

However, the practical deployment of SJF and SRTF is hindered by the need for accurate prediction of CPU burst times, an input typically unknown beforehand [2]. In dynamic and unpredictable computing environments, accurately predicting these burst times is a significant challenge. Traditional methods of burst time estimation, such as Exponential Averaging (EA), rely on historical data and mathematical heuristics, which may not be reliable under varying workloads and diverse system conditions [3].

Recent advancements in Machine Learning (ML) offer promising techniques to predict process behavior based on historical and runtime features [3] [4]. By integrating ML predictions into the decision-making process of SJF and SRTF schedulers, the system can dynamically adapt and make more informed scheduling choices, thereby improving responsiveness and efficiency. Moreover, the effective management of computing resources has become increasingly critical due to the ever-expanding use of mobile devices with constrained energy storage and heightened awareness of the environmental impact of large data centers [5]. Predicting a task’s runtime for a single machine is not sufficient since infrastructures available to scientists are frequently heterogeneous, consisting of machines with different CPU, I/O, and memory configurations [6].

As a result, this paper explores the integration of ML techniques into CPU scheduling to enhance the performance of SJF and SRTF. K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), Support Vector Machines (SVM), Decision Trees, Random Forest, XGBoost, and Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) will be used in burst

time estimation. We will delve into the potential benefits, challenges, and methodologies involved in predicting CPU burst times. The ultimate goal is to bridge the gap between the theoretical optimality of SJF/SRTF and their practical applicability, leading to more efficient and responsive operating systems.

After the introduction, the rest of the paper is organized into the following sections. Section two discusses the literature review or related work. The methodology is discussed in section three, whereas section four talks about the experimental setup and results. The interpretation of results, findings, implications, and challenges are discussed in section five. Section six concludes the paper and recommends future research directions.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The problem of accurately estimating CPU burst times has been a topic of interest in operating systems research for decades. Early approaches primarily relied on statistical methods and historical averaging, while more recent research has begun to leverage the power of ML.

A. Traditional CPU Scheduling Approaches

CPU scheduling is foundational to operating system performance, dictating how processes access limited processing resources. Classical algorithms like First-Come-First-Served (FCFS), Priority Scheduling, and Round Robin (RR) have been widely implemented due to their simplicity and ease of use [7] [8]. Among these, SJF and SRTF are acknowledged for their theoretical efficiency, particularly in reducing average waiting and turnaround times [9]. While traditional scheduling algorithms have been effective in managing CPU and memory, they often struggle with the dynamic and heterogeneous nature of modern computing environments, leading to suboptimal performance [10].

SJF, a non-preemptive approach, schedules the process with the shortest CPU burst time, while SRTF is its preemptive variant, selecting the process with the least remaining burst time at every clock tick. However, both algorithms assume prior knowledge of CPU burst durations—a major limitation in real-world applications [2]. Traditionally, Exponential Averaging (EA) has been used to estimate these burst times. EA calculates the next burst as a weighted average of previous bursts, but it is static and lacks adaptability, especially in dynamic workload environments [3]. While traditional scheduling algorithms have been effective in managing CPU and memory, they often struggle with the dynamic and heterogeneous nature of modern computing environments, leading to suboptimal performance [10]. The traditional techniques to predict burst time are summarized in Fig. 1

B. Heuristic and Fuzzy Logic-Based Estimators

To overcome the limitations of exponential averaging, several heuristic-based models have been proposed. For instance, [11] introduced a Dual-Simplex Optimization Method that improves burst time prediction by solving a linear optimization

problem. [12] applied fuzzy logic techniques to incorporate uncertainty and process variability into burst prediction. Although both approaches improved prediction accuracy, they were computationally intensive and less scalable.

C. Emergence of ML in Scheduling

Recent advances in ML have reshaped predictive scheduling. ML models can learn from historical execution data to infer complex patterns in process behavior, offering a data-driven alternative to static prediction models [3][4] were among the pioneers to employ ML techniques such as K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), Support Vector Machines (SVM), and Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) to estimate CPU burst times in computational grid environments. Their results showed substantial improvements in average waiting and turnaround times compared to EA.[13] extended this work by benchmarking ML models across diverse workloads. Their findings indicated that KNN consistently outperformed traditional methods in prediction accuracy, as measured by low Relative Absolute Error (RAE) and high Correlation Coefficient (CC).

The authors in the paper [14] propose that predicting the workload can improve the efficiency of resource management. This necessitates more sophisticated resource managers capable of efficiently utilizing diverse computational assets. [14]. For instance, cloud computing environments often employ sophisticated scheduling strategies to manage diverse tasks with varying resource requirements and priorities, including batch processing and dynamic long-term tasks [15]. These strategies often employ intricate algorithms to assign workloads efficiently, aiming to satisfy multiple objectives, such as minimizing execution time, reducing energy consumption, and optimizing resource utilization [16].

D. Integrated and Hybrid ML-Based Scheduling

Integration of ML into actual scheduling mechanisms has also been explored. The author in [4] proposed a real-time ML-driven scheduler that utilizes burst time predictions to dynamically assign CPU time. Similarly, the authors in [17] introduced the Improved Shortest Job First (IMPSJF) algorithm, which considers both the predicted burst time and the average remaining burst times of other processes to reduce starvation and enhance fairness. The paper by [3] proposes an ML-based approach to estimate CPU-burst times in computational grid environments, aiming to overcome the limitations of traditional prediction methods like EA. The study posits that ML techniques can serve as a superior alternative to conventional statistical methods for CPU-burst prediction in grid computing. Various approaches, including ML techniques, have been explored to address the complexities of resource allocation and scheduling in such environments, aiming to optimize performance and resource utilization [18] [19]. Such inefficiencies highlight the need for predictive models that can anticipate resource requirements and optimize scheduling decisions in real-time, especially in environments characterized by rapid resource variation and uncertain task loads [20].

Fig. 1. Methods to Predict Burst Time (Source: media.geeksforgeeks.org)

E. Limitations and Challenges

Despite the promising performance, ML-based scheduling systems face several challenges. Model training and prediction introduce computational overhead, especially in real-time systems with tight latency requirements. There is also the “cold start” problem, where the model lacks sufficient historical data for accurate predictions during initial deployment [4]. Additionally, the generalizability of ML models remains a concern, as models trained on one workload may not perform well under different conditions.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Research Design

This study employs an experimental research design to develop, train, and evaluate ML models for predicting CPU burst times. The primary objective is to enhance the efficiency of the SJF and SRTF CPU scheduling algorithms. The research involves simulations using a synthetic dataset designed to mimic grid workload patterns, with plans to transition to the real-world GWA-T-4 dataset. The ultimate goal is to achieve average waiting and turnaround times in the range of 0–50 ms by leveraging accurate burst time predictions and comparing these results against traditional exponential averaging methods.

B. Data Collection and Preprocessing

A synthetic dataset was used to simulate the structure of the GWA-T-4 dataset, comprising 1000 samples. The dataset includes seven features relevant to CPU scheduling:

- Process arrival time (normalized to 0–100 ms)
- Previous CPU burst length (0–50 ms)
- I/O wait time (0–20 ms)
- Priority level (1–5)
- Memory consumption (100–2000 MB)
- Number of I/O requests (0–10)

- CPU burst time (0–50 ms), generated as $0.7 \times \text{prev_cpu_burst} + 0.3 \times \text{io_wait_time} + \text{noise}$

The data was preprocessed by removing missing values and standardized using StandardScaler to ensure a uniform scale for ML algorithms. An additional feature, `io_to_burst_ratio`, was engineered to potentially improve model performance. The dataset was split into training (80%) and testing (20%) subsets using stratified sampling to maintain a representative distribution of burst times.

C. Feature Selection

Feature selection was performed using a combination of Correlation-Based Feature Selection (CFS) and Recursive Feature Elimination (RFE) to identify the most predictive attributes. This process identified three features that strongly influence CPU burst time, reducing dimensionality and minimizing the risk of overfitting:

- `io_to_burst_ratio`
- `prev_cpu_burst`
- `io_wait_time`

D. ML Models

Six ML models were employed to predict CPU burst times, with hyperparameters optimized using GridSearchCV with 5-fold cross-validation. The models and their best-performing configurations are as follows:

- K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN): Predicts burst times by averaging the values of the $k = 7$ nearest neighbors with uniform weights. Thus, given a dataset:

$$\mathcal{D} = \{(x_1, y_1), (x_2, y_2), \dots, (x_n, y_n)\}$$

where:

- $x_i \in \mathbb{R}^d$ is the feature vector of the i -th data point (with d features),
- $y_i \in \mathcal{Y}$ is the label of the i -th data point,

- n is the total number of training samples.

For a new query point $x \in \mathbb{R}^d$, the KNN proceeds as follows:

The distance between x and each training sample x_i is computed using the Euclidean distance method:

$$d(x, x_i) = \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^d (x_j - x_{i,j})^2}$$

where:

- $d(x, x_i)$ is the distance between query point x and training point x_i ,
- x_j is the j -th feature of query point x ,
- $x_{i,j}$ is the j -th feature of training point x_i ,
- d is the dimensionality of the feature space,

The selection of nearest neighbors is done by identifying the set of indices $N_k(x)$ corresponding to the k smallest distances:

$$N_k(x) = \arg \min_{S \subset \{1, \dots, n\}, |S|=k} \sum_{i \in S} d(x, x_i)$$

Where:

- k is the number of neighbors,
- $N_k(x)$ is the index set of the k nearest neighbors to x .

Prediction by majority votes was based on:

$$\hat{y}(x) = \operatorname{argmax}_{c \in \mathcal{Y}} \sum_{i \in N_k(x)} \mathbf{1}(y_i = c)$$

where:

- $\hat{y}(x)$ is the predicted class label,
- $c \in \mathcal{Y}$ is a candidate class label,
- $\mathbf{1}(\cdot)$ is the indicator function (1 if the condition is true, 0 otherwise).

Or by regression or the average of neighbors:

$$\hat{y}(x) = \frac{1}{k} \sum_{i \in N_k(x)} y_i$$

where:

- $\hat{y}(x)$ is the predicted continuous value,
- y_i is the target value of neighbor i .

Summary of Variables:

- n : number of training samples,
 - d : number of features (dimension of input space),
 - x : query (test) data point,
 - x_i : i -th training data point,
 - y_i : label or value of x_i ,
 - \mathcal{Y} : label space (set of possible classes or real values),
 - k : number of nearest neighbors,
 - $d(x, x_i)$: distance metric (commonly Euclidean),
 - $N_k(x)$: set of indices of the k nearest neighbors,
 - $\hat{y}(x)$: predicted label or value for x .
- Support Vector Machines: Uses a linear kernel with a regularization parameter $C = 10$ and an epsilon of 0.1 for regression.

For the SVM problem, a given dataset of labeled samples with the description below is considered:

$$\{(x_i, y_i)\}_{i=1}^n$$

where:

- $x_i \in \mathbb{R}^d$: feature vector of the i -th sample (dimension d).
- $y_i \in \{-1, +1\}$: class label of the i -th sample.
- n : number of training samples.

For linear decision, our SVM seeks a linear decision boundary (hyperplane) of the form:

$$f(x) = w^T x + b$$

where:

- $w \in \mathbb{R}^d$: weight vector (normal to the hyperplane).
- $b \in \mathbb{R}$: bias term (offset of the hyperplane).

The classifier assigns labels as follows:

$$\hat{y} = \operatorname{sign}(f(x)) = \operatorname{sign}(w^T x + b).$$

A Hard-Margin SVM or Linearly Separable Case formulation was based on the expressions:

$$\min_{w, b} \frac{1}{2} \|w\|^2$$

subject to

$$y_i(w^T x_i + b) \geq 1, \quad \forall i = 1, \dots, n$$

where $\|w\|$ is the Euclidean norm of w .

Finally, Soft-Margin SVM or Non-separable Case, thus, slack variables $\xi_i \geq 0$ are introduced using the expressions:

$$\min_{w, b, \xi} \frac{1}{2} \|w\|^2 + C \sum_{i=1}^n \xi_i$$

subject to

$$y_i(w^T x_i + b) \geq 1 - \xi_i, \quad \xi_i \geq 0, \quad \forall i$$

where:

- ξ_i : slack variable measuring violation of margin (misclassification).
- $C > 0$: regularization parameter controlling trade-off between margin size and misclassification penalty.

Finally, the dual formulation with Kernels ensuring the dual optimization of our problem is expressed as follows:

$$\max_{\alpha} \sum_{i=1}^n \alpha_i - \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n \alpha_i \alpha_j y_i y_j K(x_i, x_j)$$

subject to

$$\sum_{i=1}^n \alpha_i y_i = 0, \quad 0 \leq \alpha_i \leq C, \quad \forall i$$

where:

- α_i : Lagrange multipliers (dual variables).
- $K(x_i, x_j) = \phi(x_i)^T \phi(x_j)$: kernel function (inner product in feature space).

Therefore, the decision function becomes:

$$f(x) = \sum_{i=1}^n \alpha_i y_i K(x_i, x) + b$$

Only points with $\alpha_i > 0$ are **support vectors**.

6. Summary of Variables

- $x_i \in \mathbb{R}^d$: input feature vector.
 - $y_i \in \{-1, +1\}$: class label.
 - $w \in \mathbb{R}^d$: weight vector.
 - $b \in \mathbb{R}$: bias term.
 - $\xi_i \geq 0$: slack variable (soft margin).
 - $C > 0$: regularization constant.
 - $\alpha_i \geq 0$: dual variable (Lagrange multiplier).
 - $K(x_i, x_j)$: kernel function.
- **Decision Trees:** Applies hierarchical decision rules with a maximum depth of 5 and a minimum of 2 samples required to split a node. Here, a decision is defined by the mapping:

$$f : \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathcal{Y}$$

where

$$f(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_{m=1}^M c_m \cdot \mathbf{1}(\mathbf{x} \in R_m).$$

Explanation of Variables

- $\mathbf{x} \in \mathcal{X}$: Input feature vector, $\mathbf{x} = (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_d)$, where $\mathcal{X} \subseteq \mathbb{R}^d$ is the feature space with d features.
- \mathcal{Y} : Output space.
 - * For **classification**: $\mathcal{Y} = \{1, 2, \dots, K\}$, where K is the number of classes.
 - * For **regression**: $\mathcal{Y} \subseteq \mathbb{R}$.
- **Random Forest:** An ensemble of 200 decision trees, each with a maximum depth of 10, for robust predictions. Thus, multiple decision trees (200) are used here.
- **XGBoost:** A gradient boosting model with 200 estimators and a learning rate of 0.01. The prediction for a data point x_i is given as:

$$\hat{y}_i = \sum_{k=1}^K f_k(x_i), \quad f_k \in \mathcal{F}$$

where

- * \hat{y}_i = predicted output for sample i .
- * K = number of boosting rounds (trees).
- * f_k = the k -th regression tree (a function mapping from input features to a score).
- * \mathcal{F} = space of regression trees, defined by structure and leaf weights.
- **Artificial Neural Networks:** A multi-layer perceptron with a single hidden layer of 100 nodes, using the hyperbolic tangent (tanh) activation function and an L2 regularization term ($\alpha = 0.001$). For a network

with L layers, the multilayer model can be expressed as:

$$\mathbf{a}^{(l)} = f^{(l)}\left(\mathbf{W}^{(l)}\mathbf{a}^{(l-1)} + \mathbf{b}^{(l)}\right), \quad l = 1, 2, \dots, L$$

Where:

- * $\mathbf{a}^{(0)} = \mathbf{x}$ = input vector to the network
- * $\mathbf{a}^{(l)}$ = activation (output) of layer l
- * $\mathbf{W}^{(l)}$ = weight matrix of layer l
- * $\mathbf{b}^{(l)}$ = bias vector of layer l
- * $f^{(l)}(\cdot)$ = activation function of layer l
- * L = total number of layers

E. Model Evaluation Metrics

The prediction accuracy of each model was evaluated on the test dataset using the following metrics:

- **Mean Absolute Error (MAE):** Measures the average magnitude of prediction errors in milliseconds.
- **Root Mean Square Error (RMSE):** Captures the impact of larger errors more heavily.
- **Relative Absolute Error (RAE):** Normalizes the error relative to a simple baseline, where values below 1.0 indicate better performance.
- **Correlation Coefficient (CC):** Assesses the linear correlation between predicted and actual burst times, with a value closer to 1.0 being ideal.

The following table presents a summary of the model performance metrics: The results show that the ANN and

TABLE I
COMPARISON OF ML MODEL PERFORMANCE METRICS

Model	MAE	RMSE	RAE	CC
ANN	4.1338	5.2766	0.4395	0.8853
Ensemble (ANN + SVM)	4.1182	5.2626	0.4379	0.8855
SVM	4.1927	5.3056	0.4458	0.8832
XGBoost	4.4123	5.7044	0.4691	0.8600
Random Forest	4.6717	5.9763	0.4967	0.8561
K-Nearest Neighbors	4.7852	5.9957	0.5088	0.8557
Decision Tree	4.8070	6.0738	0.5111	0.8527
Baseline	20.6733	23.2376	2.1981	0.8728

the ANN+SVM Ensemble models achieved the best performance, with the lowest MAE and RAE, and the highest CC values. These models significantly outperformed the exponential averaging baseline, which had an MAE over four times greater.

F. Integration with Scheduling Algorithms

Predicted burst times were integrated into simulations of the SJF and SRTF scheduling algorithms as follows:

- 1) **Preprocessing:** Features of processes in the ready queue are extracted and standardized.
- 2) **Prediction:** The best-performing trained ML model (e.g., ANN or ensemble) predicts the CPU burst time for each process.
- 3) **Scheduling Decision:** The scheduler sorts processes based on predicted burst time (SJF) or predicted remaining time (SRTF).

Fig. 2. Algorithm Performance: Mean Absolute Error

- 4) **Execution Simulation:** A Python-based simulation engine dispatches processes according to the scheduling logic and collects performance metrics.

The simulations utilized normalized synthetic data with arrival times ranging from 0 to 100 ms and burst times ranging from 0 to 50 ms.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP, AND RESULTS DISCUSSIONS

The simulations were implemented in Python using key libraries such as scikit-learn for ML models, Pandas and NumPy for data handling, and Matplotlib/Seaborn for visualizations. Experiments were conducted on a system with an Intel Core i7 CPU, 8 GB RAM, and a Windows 10 OS.

A. Comparative Analysis

ML-based scheduling was compared against a traditional exponential averaging baseline and an "oracle" baseline, which represents the theoretical best-case performance with perfect knowledge of burst times.

B. Comparative Performance

The following table summarizes the performance of each scheduling strategy in the simulation: As shown, the ML-based scheduling strategies significantly reduced both the average waiting and turnaround times compared to the

TABLE II
COMPARISON OF SCHEDULING PERFORMANCE METRICS

Scheduling Strategy	Avg Waiting Time (ms)	Avg Turnaround Time
SJF + ANN	1483.11	1503.72
SRTF + ANN	1483.05	1503.67
SJF + Ensemble	1483.36	1503.97
SRTF + Ensemble	1483.30	1503.92
Baseline (Exponential Averaging)	1586.37	1606.98
Oracle (Perfect Predictions)	1411.23	1432.89

exponential averaging baseline, achieving an improvement of approximately 6.5%. The ML-based methods also performed remarkably close to the "oracle" baseline, with an average waiting time difference of approximately 5%.

C. Discussion of Simulation Results

While the ML-based approaches clearly outperform the baseline, the absolute values of waiting and turnaround times (~1483–1503 ms) are higher than the ideal range of 0–50 ms. This inflated value is an artifact of the simulation logic and the characteristics of the synthetic dataset, not a reflection of poor prediction quality. The fact that the ML-based simulations are within 5% of the Oracle's performance (which uses perfect knowledge) is a strong indicator of the predictive models' success. Future work will involve optimizing the simulation engine and using the real GWA-T-4 dataset to achieve the target performance range.

Fig. 3. Algorithm Performance: Root Mean Square Error

D. Discussion of Results

This subsection discusses the results based on benefits and the associated challenges.

E. Benefits of ML-Enhanced Scheduling

- **Accuracy:** The ANN and ensemble models achieved an MAE of ~ 4.12 ms, a significant improvement over the baseline (20.67 ms). This high accuracy promises efficient scheduling, especially with real-world data.
- **Adaptability:** ML models can learn complex, non-linear patterns in workload data, essential for dynamic and unpredictable grid computing environments.
- **Efficiency:** Accurate predictions result in a substantial reduction in average waiting and turnaround times compared to traditional methods, thereby enhancing overall system efficiency.

F. Challenges and Limitations

- **Simulation Issues:** The current high waiting and turnaround times are due to limitations in the simulation model, not the prediction quality of the ML models.
- **Model Generalization:** The synthetic dataset's simplicity may not fully represent the complexity of real-world workloads, which will be addressed by transitioning to the GWA-T-4 dataset.

- **Integration Complexity:** Integrating ML models at the operating system level presents engineering challenges.
- **Cold Start Problem:** Limited historical data for new processes may reduce initial prediction accuracy.

V. CONCLUSION

This study successfully demonstrates the potential of ML to enhance CPU scheduling by accurately predicting burst times for SJF and SRTF algorithms. The ANN and ANN+SVM ensemble models achieved high predictive accuracy, with MAE of ~ 4.12 – 4.13 ms and CC of ~ 0.885 . This performance represents a significant improvement over the exponential averaging baseline, with a mean absolute error (MAE) of 20.67 ms. Although the current simulation results show unrealistically high scheduling times due to model limitations, the ML-based methods are demonstrated to be within 5% of the oracle's performance. By transitioning to the real GWA-T-4 dataset and optimizing the simulation logic, the study aims to achieve target waiting times of 0 – 30 ms for SRTF and 5 – 50 ms for SJF, and turnaround times of 5 – 50 ms for SRTF and 10 – 80 ms for SJF.

Future work will focus on integrating the GWA-T-4 dataset to validate these targets in realistic grid computing environments. We will also explore lightweight ML models for real-time operating system deployment, reinforcement learning for adaptive scheduling, and hy-

Fig. 4. Algorithm Performance: Relative Absolute Error

brid ensemble models to enhance robustness and fairness. Kernel-level implementations and real-time experiments will further assess the practical scalability of ML-driven scheduling, ensuring it achieves the desired performance of 0–50ms while reducing latency, mitigating starvation, and improving energy efficiency in high-volume computing systems.

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Fig. 5. Algorithm Performance: Correlation Coefficient

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Fig. 6. Scheduling Simulation: Average Waiting Time

Fig. 7. Scheduling Simulation: Average Turnaround Time